

exp(ikx-iEt), Wave-equation and Energy-Momentum Relationships

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A wave equation already exists in classical physics (for example for a vibrating string) with a solution of the form $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ where $k=2\pi/\text{wavelength}$ and $\omega=2\pi \times \text{frequency}$. k and ω are not simply linked to momentum and energy, but the wave is physically visible.

The wavelike function $\exp(ikx-iEt)$ also appears in solutions for the photon, the relativistic Klein Gordon equation (and the Dirac too) as well as in the Schrodinger equation. This solution separates x and k and E and t so $-i\partial/\partial x \exp(ikx-iEt) = k \exp(ikx-iEt)$ and $i\partial/\partial t \exp(ikx-iEt) = E \exp(ikx-iEt)$. If a classical equation exists linking energy and momentum (like $E^2=p^2+m^2$ or $E=.5mv^2$), one may convert it into a differential equation with independent fluctuations in x and t , but linked through the energy relationship. This retains the classical information, but introduces a wave solution.

For the Schrodinger equation with a potential, $\exp(-iEt + i \int_0^x v(x) dx)$ is a solution which is equivalent to $\exp(i \int_0^t L dt)$ where L is the Lagrangian. In this case, $-i\partial/\partial x \exp(i \text{action}) = p(x) \exp(i \text{action})$ and $i\partial/\partial t \exp(i \text{action}) = E \exp(i \text{action})$. This also holds for the relativistic Lagrangian $-\frac{m}{2} \sqrt{1-v^2}$. In the case of an electromagnetic potential $v \cdot A$, one may write $\int dt v \cdot A = \int_0^x dx \dot{A}$ and so A behaves exactly like $p(x)$.

For the case of light, $\exp(ikx-iEt)$ follows as a solution of a wave equation for either the electric or magnetic fields (which follows from Maxwell's equations). The equation: $d/dt (.5\epsilon_0 E^2 + .5/\mu_0 B^2) + \text{grad} \cdot E \times B = 0$ (for no source) also follows from Maxwell's equations. It is an equation relating energy density to momentum flux and also allows for an $\exp(ikx-iEt)$ solution if E and B have the same magnitude ($c=1$) and are perpendicular to each other and the motion of the photon.

Wave Equation

The wave equation is well-known aside from photons and quantum mechanics as $\exp(ikx-iEt)$ appears as a solution to waves on a string. It is a solution of an equation based on tension (1) i.e.

$$d^2y/dx^2 = m/T d^2y/dt^2 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{Here } T \text{ is tension}$$

One may already see how x and t dependence is separated i.e. the response of y to t and to x are treated independently through the derivatives, but then linked. A solution is: $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ where $k=2\pi/(2L/n)$ and $\omega=(2\pi/n) \sqrt{T/m}$ where L is the length of the string and n an integer. One may note that k is $2\pi/\text{wavelength}$ and $\omega=2\pi \times \text{frequency}$. Thus, this solution deals with wavelength and frequency directly and not energy and momentum. The waves produced are physically visible.

Later, it was found by Maxwell that his EM equations led to a wave solution i.e. $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$, but in this case, one had not only wavelength and frequency, but energy and momentum with $\text{Energy}=\hbar \omega$ and $p=2\pi/\text{wavelength}$. (The solution followed from a wave equation for either electric field or magnetic field with no sources. We show later that $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ may also

be linked to an energy-Poynting vector equation). The waves present manifested themselves through diffraction and interference, but with Einstein's treatment of the photoelectric effect, it was seen that energy was delivered immediately instead of being spread out in a wave. Thus, a particle-wave duality seemed to already exist for the photon, with the wave aspect representing a kind of probability wave for the photon.

L. de Broglie then associated a particle, governed by Newtonian mechanics, to have a wave solution, $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$. This solution is linked to the Lagrangian, which may be used to compute Newton's equation, through $\exp(i \int_0^t L(t_1) dt_1)$ as noted by P. Dirac. The wave nature manifested itself through a two slit interference experiment.

Particle Case

The form $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ has a direct link to classical physics, both in the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases. If one considers:

$E = pv - L$ and $p = dL/dv$ with $p = mv$ (simple case) then:

$$\exp(ikx-iEt) = \exp(i \int L dt) \quad \text{if } v = x/t = \text{constant} \quad L = \int L dt \text{ for } L \text{ constant} \quad ((1b))$$

Furthermore, one may show that for $v = \text{constant} = x/t$ and $L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2}$ or $L = .5mv^2$ that:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \int L(x,t) dt) = E \exp(i \int L dt) \quad \text{and} \quad -i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(i \int L dt) = p \exp(i \int L dt) \quad ((2))$$

For the case of a potential:

$$L = -E + pv \quad (p = mv \text{ simple case}) \quad \text{so} \quad \int L dt = -Et + \int_0^x dx_1 m v(x_1) \quad ((3))$$

This is of the form: $-Et + \int_0^x p(x_1) dx_1$ thus ((2)) still holds i.e. one may vary with respect to x and t independently to get p and E . In this case, however, one must be careful with respect to the energy equation. One has:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \int_0^t L dt_1) - V(x) = \text{kinetic energy} = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(i \int_0^t L dt_1) \quad ((4))$$

" $v(x)$ " in ((3)) is a classical velocity, the square root of kinetic energy at x times $2m$.

It is interesting to note that $\exp(iEt)$, with E being a number, appears for both a free and fixed energy particle in a potential (e.g. bound particle). $\exp(i \int_0^x p(x_1) dx_1)$, however, is not $\exp(ipx)$. Rather, it may be decomposed in a Fourier series of $\exp(ipx)$, each representing a free particle:

$$\exp(i \int_0^x dx_1 p(x_1) dx_1) = \sum \text{over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{Thus, } p(x)p(x)/2m = [\sum \text{over } p \quad a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)] / [\sum \text{over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx)] \quad ((6))$$

$\int a(p) \exp(ipx) dp$ is called a wavefunction and $p(x)$ is really $p_{rms}(x)$ because it is not equal to:

$$\int a(p) \exp(ipx) dp / \int a(p) \exp(ipx) dp = \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle \quad (7)$$

Classical Result

The Schrodinger equation is usually taken to be a quantum mechanical equation. It is associated with $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ for no potential and $\exp(-iEt + \int_0^x p(x_1) dx_1)$ for a potential and is a differential equation i.e. $i \hbar \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \text{Action}) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(i \text{Action}) + V(x) \exp(i \text{Action})$. Consider that two wave solutions given directly above are expressed in terms of classical results. Using them as solutions gives:

$$E = p^2/2m \quad \text{and} \quad E = p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x)$$

where $p(x)$ is a completely classical result i.e. $p(x)p(x)/2m = KE(x)$. Thus, classical physics could be associated with $\exp(i \text{Action})$ and the Schrodinger equation. In other words, one could describe Newton's result in terms of a differential equation with a wave solution.

This begs the question, however: What is the meaning of $\exp(ipx - iEt)$? $E = KE(x) + V(x)$ is an average equation, but $\exp(ipx - Et)$ suggests periodic (wave-like) behaviour. If it is utilized, one would expect some type of wavelike behaviour in the classical problem, otherwise it is simply a mathematical tool. De Broglie suggested this wavelike behaviour does exist and leads to electron interference. Thus, there may be an "average" energy equation and with further details present which do not appear in such an equation. The Dirac equation, for example, is consistent with the Klein-Gordon wave equation or Maxwell's equations $dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B$ and $-dB/dt = \text{grad} \times E$ (no source) are both associated with a wave equation in either E or B , but give more detail.

This is perhaps more clearly seen in the case of an $A \cdot v$ potential where A is the magnetic potential from say a solenoid. In such a case, there may be no force on a charged particle, but $A \cdot v$ still appears as a potential. From the point of view of Newton's equations, this is strange as the Hamiltonian is $H = \frac{1}{2} m v^2$. From the Lagrangian, momentum $p = mv + qA$. The wave approach allows one to use a solution of $\exp(-iEt + i p_1 x + i \int_0^x qA(x_1) dx_1)$. Here p_1 is associated with mv . This shows an extra phase appearing in the wave solution even though the classical result $E = \frac{1}{2} m v^2$ still holds. The wave feature is visible in the Bohm-Aharonov experiment.

Thus, one may formulate classical physics in terms of a wave type solution to a differential equation. Ignoring the wave features, yields an energy momentum relationship such as $E = KE(x) + V(x)$, but the wave solution is suggestive of extra physics in the problem.

Photon Case

The photon wave solution for E and B i.e. electric and magnetic fields is usually taken from a solution of a wave-equation for E alone and B alone which follows from Maxwell's equations

$dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B$ and $dB/dt = -\text{grad} \times E$. For the photon, E and B are of the same strength ($c=1$) and perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion. A wave solution, however, should also emerge from:

$$d/dt (.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + d/dx E \times B = 0 \quad ((8))$$

Thus, one may link $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ to an energy-momentum type of equation. It is interesting to note that ((8)) is linear in d/dt and d/dx and contains a positive sign between the two. A wave equation uses $d/dt d/dt - d/dx d/dx (1/c^2) = 0$ or $d/dt d/dt \exp(ikx-i\omega t) = 1/c^2 d/dx d/dx \exp(ikx-i\omega t)$. In other words, a quadratic form of the derivatives is needed to deal with the negative sign in $ikx-i\omega t$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that a wave-equation is already present in classical physics to describe, for example, waves on a string. A solution of $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ exists with $k=2\pi/\text{wavelength}$ and $\omega=2\pi \times \text{frequency}$. These solutions, however, are not linked to energy or momentum. Energy and momentum seem to be associated with Newton's second law or the Lagrange equations. In this note, we argue that a wave solution may also be associated with a Lagrangian.

$\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ or $\exp(-iEt + i \int_0^x dx_1 mv(x_1))$ (for a potential) is the same as $\exp(i \text{action}) = \exp(i \int_0^t dt L(t))$ where L is the Lagrangian. $-i d/dx \exp(i \text{action}) = p(x)$ $\exp(i \text{action})$ and $i d/dt \exp(i \text{action}) = E \exp(i \text{action})$. This is usually used to establish the Schrodinger equation which is called a quantum mechanical equation. For a fixed energy situation, however, $\exp(i \text{action}) = \exp(-iEt + i \int_0^x dx_1 mv(x_1))$ is a completely classical result leading to: $E = KE(x) + V(x)$. Thus, a wave solution and a Schrodinger equation may be used to produce a classical result. One might ask, however, why a wave solution appears in such a picture. It seems that if a wave solution is present, some kind of wave (even a probability one) should be present. It seems that that is in fact the case as there is interference in electrons.

Thus, a classical average equation $E=KE(x)+V(x)$ may "wash" out some details i.e. wave like features which actually exist in a problem, but it seems that an $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ or $\exp(-iEt + i \int_0^x dx_1 mv(x_1))$ formalism may be used in conjunction with a differential equation to obtain a classical average equation. If one wishes, extra "quantum" features may then be deduced (as they are physically present). For example, $\exp(i \int_0^x dx_1 p(x_1))$ is a function of x and may be written as Fourier series i.e. $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This has the interpretation of an ensemble of free waves $\exp(ipx)$ even though there is only one $\exp(iEt)$. This leads to a statistical interpretation, we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/String_vibration